

An economic evaluation for implementation of Zero Defects and Zero Waste inspection solution in the Wind Energy manufacturing industry

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Abstract Current research aims to evaluate the return on investment for different automated inspection solutions based on selected features and incorporate this evaluation methodology in the multistage investment decision process. Hardware, dataset acquisition, and machining learning training costs are important variables in estimating the cost of automatic painting inspection equipment. This paper proposes a methodology to calculate and analyse the return on investment of an automatic visual inspection solution for painting inspection. The proposed method shows the influence of hardware selection on the inspection equipment cost, inspection cycle time, inspection cost and economic feasibility. The performance of automatic vision systems is influenced by the robustness, accuracy and time efficiency in the defect detection process; this article covers these topics and provides an early use case for painting inspection solutions. The paper remarks on the importance of inspection cost based on the inspection machine, analysing the return on investment based on the technical features selected.

Keywords: Inspection economics; Investment decision; Economic Analysis; Zero Defects; Zero Waste.

1 Introduction

As customer quality requirements increase each decade, manual inspections become costly, and the physical and metal fatigue due to repetitive tasks reduce the accuracy and reliability of the manual visual inspection (Psarommatis et al., 2020; Sarkar & Saren, 2016). The main value-driven of the Zero Defects Manufacturing (ZDM) industrial model is sustained in three pillars: sustainability, resilience, and human-centricity (Reichenstein et al., 2022; Rožanec et al., 2022). The development of

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information technologies and sensors boosts the implementation of automatic in-line non-destructive inspections, replacing manual processes, reducing personnel costs, enhancing reliability and accuracy, and improving inspection efficiency (Rožanec et al., 2022; Zhou et al., 2023). In the ZDM strategy, non-destructive inspection technologies focus on executing repetitive inspection tasks that are conventionally performed out of the line manually or even with destructive methods (Rožanec et al., 2022; Zhou et al., 2023).

One key business goal is quality assurance, which builds customer trust, improves customer loyalty, and strengthens brand reputation (Arinez et al., 2020; Galindo-Salcedo et al., 2022). In the painting and coating industry processes, defects such as pits, holes, underfill, and scratches appear due to failures related to equipment, raw materials, or conditions in the production environment. The painting on the wind tower acts as a surface treatment to increase the corrosion resistance of the steel; in the long term, this corrosion mechanism can result in equipment failure due to the high demand conditions of the offshore environment. The painting defects increase the costs incurred by the manufacturers, including reprocessing, warranty, and reputation costs, and they reduce the product's service life.

Failures during painting, coating or surface treatment are nearly impossible to avoid due to the influence of environmental conditions, the state of production resources, and the variability of the raw materials (Bai et al., 2024; Luo et al., 2020). Manual visual inspection is the conventional technique for detecting defects in painting or coating treatments. According to industrial associations, the reliability, accuracy and defection efficiency of manual inspection are low and depend on the mental and physical fatigue of the operator (Prunella et al., 2023). Painting defects in a wind tower structure may lead to an elevated economic impact and reputation losses for the wind energy sector Tier manufacturers. The painting process quality can be improved if the visual inspection is performed by an automated vision system rather than inspection performed by operators.

The cost of the inspection policies is directly related to four main factors: the time of inspection (online or offline), the type of inspection (non-destructive or destructive), the inspected quantity (full batch or sampling), and the nature of the inspection (manual or automatic) (Bose & Guha, 2021; Mezher & Marble, 2024). Implementing full inspection policies based on an automatic inspection system, supported by artificial intelligence for decision-making, reduces the inspection cost and minimises the possibility of defective products reaching the customer (Reichenstein et al., 2022). The main innovation of the presented research is to combine non-destructive inspection technologies and cost breakdown methodology to calculate the equipment inspection cost, which is directly related to automatic inspection cost.

This paper employs a breakdown cost estimation to evaluate the total inspection cost based on the features selected to design the automated visual inspection equipment. The proposed approach is a helpful tool for NDIT solution providers and managers of manufacturing companies to assess the impact of technical requirements and quality inspections in the early stages of the design of non-destructive inspection solutions.

2 Methodology

The current article examines how different automated visual inspection solutions configurations can affect equipment cost, the return on investment (ROI), and Pay-back Period (PbP). Three different scenarios are studied in current proposals, the different between them is the number of cameras installed on the automated visual inspection equipment (Fig. 1).

The cost of automated visual inspection equipment has been broken down into hardware, data acquisition, labelling, machine learning, and software development costs (Table 1). The hardware cost has been estimated depending on the number of cameras/lenses/light source selected per scenario and considering other components such as Programmable Logic Controller (PLC), Human Machine Interface (HMI), or Automated Guided Vehicle (AGV), among other components. The data acquisition cost has been determined by multiplying the average time employed to detect and record one painting defect multiplied by the labor rate considered and the number of data required to train the artificial algorithm (2.000 images). The labelling cost has been calculated using the average time employed by a skilled operator to classify and label the images. The machine learning cost has been estimated based on the time employed to train a machine learning model, which depends on the dataset size (4.000 images), the size of the images employed, the hyperparameters selected and the hardware employed. The software development cost has been estimated to adapt the inspection software to customer requirements. The total equipment inspection cost is obtained by adding the hardware cost, data acquisition cost, labelling cost, machine learning cost, and software development cost.

Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
- Camera sensors: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of cameras: 2 • CMOS sensor. • 20 Megapixels • Power supply: 2. • Visible Spectrum. 	- Camera sensors: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of cameras: 4. • CMOS sensor. • 20 Megapixels • Power supply: 4 • Visible Spectrum 	- Camera sensors: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of cameras: 6. • CMOS sensor. • 20 Megapixels • Power supply: 6 • Visible Spectrum
- Optical lens: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of lens: 2. • Focal length 25 mm. • 30 x 20 cm FOV. 	- Optical lens: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of lenses: 4. • Focal length 25 mm. • 30 x 20 cm FOV. 	- Optical lens: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of lenses: 6. • Focal length 25 mm. • 30 x 20 cm FOV.
- Light source: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of bar lights: 4. • LED. • Bar length: 500 mm. • Power supply: 4. 	- Light source: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of bar lights: 8. • LED. • Bar length: 500 mm. • Power supply: 8. 	- Light source: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of bar lights: 12. • LED. • Bar length: 500 mm. • Power supply: 12.

Fig. 1 Schematic representation of three scenario proposed for the automated visual inspection equipment.

Once the equipment cost is estimated the inspection cost for the different scenarios (manual or automated inspection) can be obtained following the same cost breakdown methodology. The proposed approach permits the estimation of painting inspection cost relative to the cost associated with the labor, amortization, and administrative cost. The inspection cost estimation model employed present a hierarchical

structure (Niazi et al., 2006). Direct labor cost includes time required to perform the Wind Tower painting inspection (18 hours), multiply by the European hourly rate (30,5 €/h). The direct labor benefit has been estimated multiplying the EU average labor expenses (21 %) per direct labor cost. Indirect activity cost includes depreciation, utilities, maintenance, and administrative activities imputable to the painting inspection operation. The capitalized cost assigned to the automated inspection machine consists of the machine depreciation rate. The depreciation rate is calculated based on the number of wind towers inspected (196 units) per year and the amortization period considered (5 years).

Table 1. Cost breakdown for automated visual inspection equipment.

Elementary components	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
Hardware	40.742	48.491	56.666
Optical sensor	1.587	1.836	4.762
Optical lens	1.957	3.914	5.872
Light source	3.941	7.071	7.882
PLC / HMI	2.800	3.920	5.040
AGV	22.000	22.000	22.000
CPU / GPU	4.000	4.000	4.000
Others	4.457	5.748	7.111
Data acquisition	9.100	9.100	9.100
Labelling	3.033	3.033	3.033
Machine learning model	2.474	2.474	2.474
Software development	25.000	25.000	25.000
Total	80.350	88.098	96.274

3 Results and discussion

The use of labor and destructive testing for quality assurance purpose increases the inspection cost, also this type of activities increase lead times, requires the intermediary inventories which increase the cost due their management and resource consumed. Non-destructive inspection solutions can have a positive impact in the quality assurance policies, impacting positively the company's economic sustainability. The capability of autonomous machine vision systems to detect painting defects during wind tower production is crucial for quality assurance, ensuring the final product quality. To improve manufacturing performance in the wind energy sector, it is important that the NDIT solutions send feedback to the manufacturing process to repair, reprocess or adjust process parameters to decrease energy and materials consumption, as well as productive resources.

In all manufacturing processes when the process shifts from an in-control state to an out-of-control the occurrence of defective parts may increase. In order to avoid those defective parts reach the customer's, the quality policies are implemented in the production. By deploying automatic visual inspection equipment's the inspection policies can be improved, minimizing the dispatch of defective products, and improving warranty periods. In case wind energy sector, the warranty periods have great importance, since the warranty cost of offshore wind towers can present elevated cost in repair, labor, and replacement activities. Clearly, the inspection

capacity improves with systems with more cameras and reduces the inspection times compared to conventional manual inspections performed by operators (Table 2). Therefore, if the automatic inspection cost can be estimated during the early design stage of automatic visual inspection equipment, solution providers and managers have tools to properly select technical specifications and evaluate the return on investment of inspection equipment.

Table 2. Detailed cost breakdown for wind tower painting inspection.

Elementary components	Manual Inspection	Automatic Insp. Sce. 1	Automatic Insp. Sce. 2	Automatic Insp. Sce. 3
Direct costs (€/unit)	664	7	7	7
Direct labor (€/unit)	549	6	6	6
Direct labor benefits (€/unit)	115	1	1	1
Indirect costs (€/unit)	151	187	196	206
Capitalized costs (€/unit)	85	167	175	183
Automatic vision system (€/unit)	N/A	82	90	98
Installation operating (€/unit)	85	85	85	85
Allocated cost (€/unit)	N/A	16	18	20
Administrative costs (€/unit)	66	3	3	3
Total (€/unit)	816	194	204	214
ROI (%)	N/A	151	136	122
PbP (months)	N/A	8	9	10
Inspection velocity (hours/unit)	18	4,6	2,3	1,5

4 Conclusions

This research has employed a breakdown cost estimation model that can be employed in the early evaluation process for integrating non-destructive inspection technologies into automatic inspection equipment. By employing this method, an extension of the model can be developed for other non-destructive inspection technologies based on an artificial intelligence framework.

The automatic inspection equipment cost estimation and inspection cost model have been validated through the Wind Tower case study and help with selecting and comparing desired features of the ZDZW solution. This work is part of an ongoing EU research project that aims to develop non-destructive inspection solutions that can be employed to reduce the consumption of energy and materials in the manufacturing process.

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